

Fiber Optic Structural Monitoring of Concrete Beam Repaired by Composite Sheets

Ki-Soo Kim

Graduate School of Venture, Hoseo University
Mt.29-1, Sechul-Ri, Baebang-Myun, Asan City, Chung-nam, 336-795, South Korea
Tel) +82-41-540-5891, Fax) +82-41-533-7437
E-mail; kisoo@office.hoseo.ac.kr

ABSTRACT

In order to extend the life time of building and civil infra-structure, nowadays, patch type fibrous composite retrofitting materials are widely used. Retrofitted concrete columns and beams gain the stiffness and strength, but they lose toughness and show brittle failure. Usually, the cracks of concrete structures are visible with naked eyes and the status of the structure in the life cycle is estimated with visible inspection. After retrofitting of the structure, crack visibility is blocked by retrofitted composite materials. Therefore, structural monitoring after retrofitting is indispensable and self diagnosis method with optical fiber sensor is very useful. In this paper, we try to detect peel out effect and find the strain difference between main structure and retrofitting patch material when they separate each other. In the experiment, two fiber optic Bragg grating sensors are applied to the main concrete structure and the patching material separately at the same position. The sensors show coincident behaviors at the initial loading, but different behaviors after a certain load.

Key word: concrete structure, repair, fiber optic, self diagnosis, monitoring

1. Introduction

Patch type retrofitting composite materials are widely used for repairing civil infrastructure nowadays. Composite material increases load bearing capacity and confines crack opening. Fiber composites are several times stronger than ordinary repairing materials such as steels and have almost the same stiffness as steel. They are very effective for repairing and retrofitting of reinforced concrete structures. They show elastic behavior up to near fracture and their specific gravity is much smaller than other repairing materials. Because the specific gravity is 1/5 of the specific gravity of steel, the fiber composites don't increase the dead load much and they are very easy to handle without special tools in very small working spaces. According to the locations of damage and the damaged conditions, we can add or drop the number of composite layers and control the load bearing capability of repaired structures.

For monitoring of the repaired structure with composite materials, optical fiber sensors are very convenient, because crack visibility is blocked by repaired materials. The fiber sensors are very small and very similar to the fibers in the composite. They also have several merits such as electro-magnetic immunity, long signal transmission, good accuracy and multiplicity of one sensor line. The strain measurement technologies with fiber optic sensors are investigated from 1980's by several authors¹⁾⁻⁴⁾. We also investigated the possibilities of fiber optic sensor application in various fields such as composites, bridges, buildings and roads⁵⁾⁻⁷⁾. We expect that the fiber optic sensors replace electrical strain gauges. The commercial electric strain gauges show good stability and dominate the strain measurement market. However they lack of durability and long term stability for continuous monitoring of the structures. In order to apply the strain gauges we only have to attach them to the surfaces of the structures. For optical fiber sensors we can embed them inside the composites or interface between composites and concrete structure. We also can use various packages for evaluation of the structure⁸⁾⁻⁹⁾. In this paper we investigate the effective mixing ratio for hybrid composites for repairing concrete and apply the fiber optic sensors to the reinforced concrete. We are trying find the self diagnostic methods to give early alarm for the separation of composites and the main structure which is most probable damage in retrofitted structures.

2. Principles of Fiber Optic Sensors

Among typical fiber optic sensors, fiber Bragg grating sensors (FBGs) and fiber optic Fabry-Perot sensors are widely used. Fiber optic Fabry-Perot sensor is very sensitive but it is very difficult to produce by the automated mass production process and its signal treatment is very complicated. On the other hand, fiber Bragg gratings can be produced by mass production equipments and they have very good reproducibility. Their signal processing is rather simple. Many of previous investigators chose fiber gratings as sensors and we also choose FBGs for structural monitoring sensors.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of FGB sensor signal

2.1 Strain Measurement Principle with Fiber Bragg Grating

Fiber Bragg grating produced by exposing ultraviolet laser through the phase mask which gives the periodical patterns to the Ge doped core. As you see in Figure 1, broad band incident beam is introduced to the grating and a specific narrow band wavelength beam reflects. The wavelength of the reflected beam relates to the periodicity of the pattern in the core. Figure1 shows schematic diagram of FBG. Only the part of the incident beam which satisfies the condition of Equation (1) reflects from the FBG and rest of the incident beam transmits. We call the wavelength of reflected beam which is in Equation (1) Bragg wavelength.

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda \quad (1)$$

n : effective refractive index, Λ : grating period

Bragg wavelength which reflect from the grating is a function of effective refractive index. Bragg wavelength is changed by temperature and strain variation. Therefore we can measure the temperature and strain by measuring Bragg wavelength. The center wavelength shift of the grating according to applied strain change is described in Equation (2) where P_e : photo-elastic constant, ϵ : applied strain to the grating

$$\Delta\lambda_B = \lambda_B(1 - P_e)\epsilon \quad (2)$$

3. Evaluation of FBG sensors with steel reinforced concrete

3.1 Preparation of specimens

In order to characterize adhesion properties and the response of FBG sensors, steel reinforced concrete specimens with the dimension of $15 \times 25 \times 180$ cm are produced. The data from FBG sensors for applied

tensile and compressive loads are compared to the electric strain gauges at the same location. The specifications and properties of the specimens are as follows.

	design purpose	materials	
		Steel	Concrete
CTL □	Tensile strain	2@D13(Tension) 2@D10(Compression)	$\sigma_{ck}=270\text{kg/cm}^2$
CTL □	Compressive strain	2@D13(Tension) 2@D10(Compression)	$\sigma_{ck}=270\text{kg/cm}^2$

3.2 Testing procedure

In order to prevent breakage of the fiber optic sensors, two pieces of metal islands are attached to the specimen and the fiber sensor is attached on them. The gage lengths of the sensors represent the distances between 2 islands which are 85 cm in the side of specimen and 75 cm in the bottom of the specimen. Strain gages are attached at the locations which are the centers of the fiber sensors. To detect the compressive strain, the fiber sensor is stretched and prestressed by force. The responses of the sensors are observed while loads apply by 4-point bending.

Figure

2. Specimen for tensile test (CTL □)

Figure 3. Specimen for compressive test with embedded steel (CTL □)

3.3 Test results

Under cyclic loading up to 40% of fracture strength, the optical fiber sensors in CTL □ are almost identical to the strain gauges at the same location. Strain gauges show breakage due to crack after a certain loading while fiber optic sensors show good responses. Fiber optic sensor shows residual values after unloading while strain gauges cannot give any data due to failure. (Figure 5.)

Figure 4. Results from strain gauge & FBG sensor for tensile test (CTL □)

Figure 5. Results from strain gauge & FBG sensor for compressive test (CTL □)

Figure 6. Results from strain gauge & FBG sensor for embedded steel (CTL □)

4. Design and Evaluation of retrofitting method using FBG sensors

4.1 Preparation of specimens

The reinforced concrete beam of 15cm×25cm section and effective depth ($d=21\bullet$) was manufactured for bending test. The amount of reinforcement was designed with maximum ratio of reinforcement ($\rho_{\max} = 0.75$, $\rho_b = 0.01466$), using compression bar of 2-D10, tension bar of 2-D13s, length 2.8m, rectangular form double layered reinforced beam which effective span length is 2.4m by standard. Then, shear reinforcement did D10 reinforcing rod to 10• space to check breaking of shear of test specimen (figure 7). Shape of specimen for bending test is same with figure 7. Also, the effect of repair□retrofit and behavior at shear loading was observed by using the beam of 10cm×10cm section and 40• length. Shape of specimen for shear test is same with figure 8.

Detail of FBG Sensor

Figure 7. Dimensions of bending test specimens and details of FBG sensors

Figure 8. Dimensions of shear test specimens

4.2 Testing method

While carbon fiber has excellent performance than other fiber, but carbon fiber sheet is weak in fire, glass fiber has fire protecting performance and less detachment than carbon fiber. Therefore, in case of reinforcement with mixing these two fibers, reinforcement performance and the most efficient mixture of

composite material was investigated. We try to find most effective mixture of the retrofitting composite material mixing glass fiber and carbon fiber that is used widely (presented in figure 9). In this paper bending test of GCO (mixture of glass fiber and carbon fiber) and GGO (mixture of glass fibers), new monitoring techniques are developed which can give an alarm of peel out at early stage that is shortcoming of general retrofitting composite material, as strain differences between the side and the bottom of reinforced concrete beam with retrofitting materials are compared. On the other hand, in case of shear test with figure 10, FBG sensors are protected by using smallest steel pipe in the interval of composite materials and also between reinforced concrete beam and retrofitting composite materials, then alarming method in peel out are tried with monitoring of strain differences at that point.

Figure 9. Combinations of lay-ups in hybrid type repairing patch

Figure 10. Combinations of lay-ups in shear specimen and embedded FBG sensors

4.3 Test Results

In two cases of bending test, it is estimated that GCO's case (figure 11) is more efficient than GGO of figure 11 because GCO of physically high strength has less danger of sudden brittle failure. Then, both GGO and GCO have the strain differences between the side and the bottom and these are proved to be effective monitoring of peel out. In the shear test that small steel pipes are used for protecting FBG sensors, it is also proved that can be effective monitoring of peel out.

Figure 11. Bending test result from the beam strengthened with two glass fiber sheets

Figure 12. Bending test result from the beam strengthened with one glass fiber sheet and one carbon fiber sheet

Figure 13. Shear test result from the beam strengthened with two carbon fiber sheets

5. Conclusions

In this paper, efficient mixture of retrofitting composite materials and fiber optic sensor measuring technology can be applied to predict peel out for retrofitted structures. Especially, strain patterns of FBG sensor at the bottom of Concrete and the carbon fiber sheet show coincident behaviors at the initial loading, but different behaviors after a certain load. It is a good example that two structural systems show different behaviors after a certain load. we used this to observe status of the structure, and the reason can be found in delamination between concrete crack and carbon fiber sheet. Using these results, the effective amount of structural reinforcement and the time of additional retrofit can be estimated, and the expense also can be reduced that follow in regular diagnosis of structural safety for maintenance of structures. To establish more systematic and quantitative standard, it is sure that development of optical fiber measure technology and accumulation of experimental sources about retrofitting composite materials are needed.

Acknowledgement

The work done in this paper was supported by KOSEF through Smart Infrastructure Technology Center in KAIST, Korea.

References

- (1) Laura De Lorenzis, Brian Miller & Antonio Nanni, "Bond of Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Laminates to Concrete" ACI Materials Journal, May-June 2001.
- (2) Kin-tak Lau, Libo Yuan, Li-min Zhou & Jingshen Wu, Chung-ho Woo "Strain monitoring in FRP laminates and concrete beams using FBG sensors" Composite Structures 51(2001), 9-20

- (3) Sarah E. Mouring & Oscar Barton, Naval Academy, D.Kevin Simmons "External Retrofit of R/C Beams using Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer Laminates" Stanford Univ, USA. Structural Faults & Repair conference, 2001
- (4) K. S. Kim, et'al, "A Model of Embedded Fiber Optic Fabry-Perot Temperature and Strain Sensors," Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 27, pp 1618 - 1662, 1993.
- (5) K. S. Kim, et'al, "Embedded Intrinsic Fabry-Perot Optical Fiber Sensors in the Cement Concrete Structure", SPIE Vol.2718, pp218-231, 1996.
- (6) J. W. Yoo, et'al, "In-situ Monitoring of Sungsan Bridge in Han River with a Optical Fiber Sensor System", SPIE Vol.3043, pp72-76, 1997.
- (7) S. H. Baek, et'al, "Optical Fiber Monitoring System of Bridge in Korea", Proceeding of the 1st Health Monitoring Workshop, pp555-563, Stanford Univ., 1997.
- (8) K. S. Kim, et'al, "The Effect of Embedded Sensors on The Strength of Composite Laminates, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites," Vol. 11, pp 949 - 958, 1992.
- (9) K. S. Kim, et'al, "The use of Strain Measurement for Detecting Delamination in Composite Laminates, Composite Structures," Vol. 23, pp 75 - 84, 1993.